

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILL IN COMMUNICATION

Umarova Feruza Nigmatovna

Teacher, English Department,

'Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization
Engineers' National Research University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to explain the importance of speaking skill in the communication process and to highlight the advantages of Speaking skill and its development. Speaking skills are an important tool for all students who want to advance their careers, improve their business, increase their self-confidence, have good job opportunities, speak in public, participate in interviews, participate in discussions and group discussions, and make presentations. Nowadays, there is a need for a speaking skill to succeed in all endeavors.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are 4 basic skills, which are listening, reading, writing and speaking skills. Listening and reading from them are considered passive or receptive skills because students do not demonstrate their talents in demonstrating these skills, but only receive information from the outside. They only listen to information available in the language or read a written statement of information or reality without any elements. However, students need to think and express their thoughts independently, and they need to practice a lot and learn a lot about grammar, vocabulary, sentence structure, and usage. Speech and writing are therefore considered active and effective skills. The Importance of Speech Skills In

today's global world, communication plays an important role in achieving success in all areas. We are a family with an environment that expresses the world that exists in our minds through this single language tool. Language is used as a means of communication. Perfect communication is impossible for people without using language. Also, people cannot achieve their goals, aspirations, and decisions without using the right language to communicate. Therefore, the need for language to communicate with people around the world is always felt. English is an international language that serves the purpose of communicating with people living in different regions, states, countries and continents of the world as a language

spoken all over the world. Speech skills are the most important skill for learning a foreign or second language. Speaking among the four basic language skills is the most important and necessary skill in learning a foreign or second language.

The questions of the scientific work are as follows:

- What is speaking skill and what is communication skill?
- What does the formation of speaking skill depend on?
- What are the benefits of developing a speaking skill??

The development of the speaking skill has always been important, and we will reveal its important aspects by finding answers to questions in the scientific process.

II. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

As Brown and Yuke (1983) say, "speaking is a skill that students value most in real-life situations". Despite its importance, speaking skills training has not been adequately assessed, and most EFL / ESL teachers continue to teach speaking skills such as memorizing conversations or repeating exercises. However, the modern world creates a demand for communication skills for students, and English teachers need to teach English learners the skills they need so that they can improve their speaking skills and become realistic. should work well in life situations. In today's English language teaching environment, great emphasis is placed on deep teaching of oral speaking skills, the formation of communicative competence in them, which is even more important in the development of students' speaking skills in the school process. Since very little attention is paid to important elements such as phonological, morphological, semantic, and syntactic

aspects of language, it is not difficult to see that it has a negative impact on English learners' acquisition of speaking skills throughout the learning process. It is well known that in the 19th and 20th centuries, the grammar translation method was the most widely used method, through which only attention was paid to reading and writing skills. Nowadays, after realizing the importance of oral communication skills, they now focus more on developing speaking skills so that students can continue their studies successfully and succeed in their fields after graduation. In addition, English is valued as the language of success in getting a job and achieving the desired goals in life. Certificates or references of language proficiency are required regardless of the field of work. As Bueno, Madrid, and McLaren (2006: 321) point out, "Speaking is one of the most difficult skills that language learners face. Speech is one of the most important of the four language skills of English and even English speakers learn for so many years; they find it difficult to speak in real time situations when it is demanded."

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

There are a number of reasons for this, the most important being that English learners should understand the importance of speaking skills and try to master them when they need to be able to compete in this competitive world. Speaking seems more difficult than other skills. For foreign or second language learners, composing sentences without learning grammatical structures and knowing enough vocabulary correctly is a noreal event. Therefore, English language learners face many problems in speaking grammatical

sentences in English. Because speech skills play a key role in communication, people all over the world try to learn these skills in order to communicate well with the whole community. In addition, these speaking skills are also essential for students to become good professionals in the future. In the demands of the modern world, the interview method has become the most effective and widely used method in the work process, rather than the survey.

B. Instruments

Speaking skills are the most important not only in the recruitment process but also in all life processes such as conversation, communication, debate, negotiation, exchange of ideas. Professionals should also make oral presentations as they promote their products or companies or conduct trainings for other colleagues. In addition, an effective speaker can inspire the audience a lot and gain the full attention of the audience and maintain the same tempo until the end of the speech. Thus, listeners are fully involved in the speaker's speech, and they sometimes forget the real world and pay full attention to the speech. Thus, speech skills play an important role because

it all depends on how people convey their messages to others.

C. Participants

Speaking skills are an essential tool for all students who want to improve their career, improve their business, increase self-confidence, have good job opportunities, speak in public, participate in interviews, participate in discussions and group discussions, make presentations. In the modern world, everything is connected with speech skills. A person with good public speaking skills can conquer the whole world. All speakers are considered as a participants of this research work.

D. Data Collection and Analysis

Good communication is the ticket to good job opportunities. In modern interviews, the real potential of entrepreneurs is tested through indicators such as group discussions, debates, presentation skills, and so on. Therefore, candidates must have good oral communication skills in order to be well placed. Once students practice these speaking skills in English classes, they will acquire these skills and excel in and out of the classroom. Let's discuss the purpose of teaching speaking skills in English lessons.

Figure 1. What is speaking?

In this global world, we need to share our ideas and thoughts with people all over the world in order to realize our desires and actions. This is a competitive world and every English learner wants to improve their speaking skills in order to be sustainable in this global market. In addition, much of the choice at work depends on the communication skills of people, especially speech skills. Interlocutors also quickly recognize personal talents in the form of conversational skills. Job seekers who can now prove their skills are the best in their careers. In addition, these conversational skills are useful for professionals to develop their careers.

In addition, these interviewing skills will be useful to employees working in commercial organizations to promote their business. Great, great and inspiring speakers are known to be highly motivated and captivate the audience. Because language skills are important in so many ways, students who

learn other language should pay more attention to them. In addition, teachers are encouraged to implement several helpful strategies to get students more involved in learning English in the classroom. Through regular exercise, English language learners can greatly improve their speaking skills. They then successfully participate in class discussions and debates and gradually develop their speaking skills. They are able to submit themselves on their own, leaving all their fears in their heads. By practicing these skills regularly, they can give a short speech in class. In addition, they build mutual trust and become stronger in decision making and problem solving. Students can also develop strong business relationships with other business partners and promote their business well. In addition, language learners do well in job interviews, so they are more likely to advance in their careers. They know how to work well with their colleagues and try to develop their careers. Thus, speaking skill

plays an important role in the overall development of students' future.

Speakers express themselves in a thoughtful, persuasive, and passionate way

through their speaking skills. There are three different speech situations: interactive, partially interactive, and non-interactive.

Figure 2. Types of speaking situation

Phone calls and face-to-face conversations include interactive speaking situations in which speaking and listening in English are an alternative. In an interactive speech setting, there will be an opportunity to ask the interviewer to repeat, explain, or ask for a slower speech. Therefore, interactive speech situations are more useful situations for both the speaker and the listener, as they can no doubt understand the issue. In partially interactive situations, the speech is delivered to a live audience and the audience does not interrupt the speaker's speech. In partially interactive conversations, the speaker can see the audience directly, as well as determine from

their facial expressions and gestures whether the participants understood his or her speech. Here, listeners can identify their doubts through a question-and-answer session (question and answer) that usually occurs at the end of the speech. In contrast to these two, in a non-interactive speech setting, there will be no interaction of listeners who have to record only their speeches for radio broadcasting.

IV. RESULTS

Being proficient in every skill is necessary to be a versatile communicator, but the ability to speak skilfully gives speakers a number of distinct advantages. It includes many key benefits of speaking skills.

BENEFITS OF SPEAKING SKILLS	
1.	To participate actively in pair or group activities in the classrooms.
2.	To give a maiden and impressive speech on different occasions.
3.	To participate actively in debates and group discussions
4.	To develop critical thinking among the learners

5.	To pursue higher studies in foreign countries
6.	To interact with people all around the globe
7.	To get better employment opportunities
8.	To perform well in job interviews
9.	To acquire more knowledge
10.	To make use of the internet effectively
11.	To make living abroad simpler and easier
12.	To promote the sale of products in the business
13.	To highly motivate and attract the customers in buying the products.
14.	To improve the overall development of the speaker's personality.
15.	To increase the ability of problem-solving and critical thinking.
16.	To get better employment opportunities all over the world.
17.	To interact with people all around the world
18.	To keep over cognition and reasoning very sharp
19.	To boost up the speakers' self-confidence.
20.	To know the different cultures of the world.
21.	To increase the income of the individual.
22.	To communicate effectively with others
23.	To give presentations for all purposes.
24.	To earn high respect in the society.
25.	To do good international business.
26.	To travel to a foreign country.
27.	To earn high salary and money in a work.

Table 1: Advantages of speaking skill

It can be continued as this list with many important and valuable aspects. Realizing that there are many benefits to speaking skills, English teachers need to pay more attention to these skills so that young people can work on them and begin their efforts to improve their speaking skills and should give them the best priority as they are very useful for the overall development of English learners.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Speaking in all of these situations is a major problem for ELLs because it involves so much and it is not easy to develop good speaking skills in a day or two. In addition, ELLs need to practice regularly and devote more time to their speaking skills because it

is very difficult to master them without proper practice. Therefore, the best way for ELLs to improve their speaking skills is to focus more on practicing their speaking skills in and out of the classroom.

Although there are other skills in English, speaking skills that show a clear expression of speaking skills are the most effective among the skills, as most communication is done through speech. Speech skills are therefore the most important method of communication.

In general, there is a need for teachers to think of different techniques and speaking skills to develop students' oral communication, which is the most important thing in the modern world.

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